

Appendix D

Additional information on materials and scales

Information about the creation of tweets

Each tweet was created as realistically as possible and included a profile photo, a username, and the publication date to increase ecological validity. No information on the number of likes, retweets, and comments were presented to avoid possible influence of virality metrics and comments on the perception of message influence, behavioral intentions, and opinions (e.g., Kim, 2018; Lee & Jang, 2010; Metzger et al., 2010; Winter et al., 2015). The tweets used a combination of affiliative humor and/ or rhyme. Affiliative humor is characterized by a benevolent, self-accepting way to charm and amuse others and has been found to influence one's relationship with others positively (Martin, 2007). Rhyme enhances perceived humor and elicits more positive affective responses (Menninghaus et al., 2014). Styles of humor potentially harming the relationship between organization and stakeholders (see Kim et al., 2016), such as aggressive humor (Martin et al., 2003), were avoided. One tweet used was adapted from the Berliner Verkehrsbetriebe (Weil wir dich lieben, 2019).

Reliabilities

Information on reliabilities of each measure in each scenario presented can be found in table D1.

Table D1

Reliabilities for the subscales per scenario

Scale	Reliability coefficient		
	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Positive affect	.87	.87	.89
Negative affect	.72	.76	.68
Trust in the local government	.88	.91	.88
Willingness to follow advice	.45	.42	.38
Willingness to seek information	.45	.42	.38
Secondary crisis communication	.52	.60	.66
Attributed crisis responsibility	.90	.91	.94
Perceived humor	.96	.96	.95

Note. For scales consisting of two items the split-half reliability was conducted. For scales with more of two items Cronbach's alpha was used as reliability coefficient.

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